

Festival and Bio Safety: an Overview

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Introduction

Festivals are like chemical bonds and bind people to enhance brotherhood and faith among members in a society irrespective of religion, caste, profession and even nationality. Since I am an Indian and have lived in many countries/ regions (the United States, Central America, Caribbean, Middle East, etc.), I can understand the festivals - Deepavali, Christmas, Eid, very well and also their importance. People, irrespective of their economic and social status, celebrate these festivals with enthusiasm. People exchange sweets and gifts and celebrate the festival day as a day of pleasure in this era of pressure. Though the festivals are religious but people celebrate it irrespective of their religions. The festivals are important social factors for unity and integrity among people at the national and international level. The festival season is highly considered as an auspicious season in the year. In festival season, people buy new items - clothes, gifts, ornaments, food items, etc., and hence there is also a growth in economy.

A festival, including new-year eve, will be healthy when there are no firecrackers. Where there are firecrackers, then the festival will be toxic to our environment. Firecrackers will release significant quantities of toxic substances when they are burst and it leads to unusual problems.

Firecrackers will lead to air, water, and noise and soil pollution. Generally, smoke from fireworks that contain pollutants can easily enter into the body through the lungs at the first instant. We can also notice that dust as a minor contributor of many pollutants [1]. As we understand, fire crackers - smoke, is a general threat for asthmatic patients. It is also one of the factors that indulged in green house effect. Fireworks contaminants can be easily carried out by rain and other usual means to lakes, rivers and oceans. The noise of fireworks can travel for a long distance. It can also have the ability to damage hearing sound of human beings and also pet animals or other animals.

-Elderly people, pregnant women, infants/children and patients may suffer from the fear of fireworks. Children may even eat firecrackers (as gums, sweets, etc.).

-Firework phobia is common among domestic animals. The noise of fire work causes fear, stress and anxiety among wild animals. Thus, wild animals get into roadways and cause damage to their own life, human life and properties (home, vehicles, etc). Birds also abandon their nests and hopeless while in fireworks.

-Firecrackers may damage properties (trees, huts, vehicles, etc.).

The Major Constituents of Firecrackers and their Effects

Copper	:	Inhalation of copper irritates respiratory tract.
Magnesium	:	Leads to blisters.
Manganese	:	Leads to emotional disturbances.
Zinc	:	Can affect central nervous system.
Cadmium	:	Inhalation of cadmium can cause anemia.
Lead	:	Affects central nervous system.

We should celebrate festivals, but without polluting our nature. Usually, at the time of Fire works, we need to shut down all the windows and doors. If we have domestic animals, we can keep them near to us to get rid of fear from fire works [2]. Forest officials and other authorities are responsible to take care of wild animals in the festival season. Certain type of ear plugs, masks and other reliable devices will be helpful to prevent the c phobia. Veterinarians are the most important members to protect domestic and wild animals from the fire works through different strategic methods [3,4]. Government and social organizations should follow-up strict policy to get rid of fire works at certain extent. All human beings who are indulged in fire works should think of other human beings, animals and the environment. That is, we have to maintain our human nature and the nature of our environment. There is a beauty in the nature and "A thing of beauty is joy forever."

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